

Five Familiar Factors Retarding the Growth of Polymer Composites in Automotive Applications

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SUMMARY

The purpose of this paper is to provide an overview of the need, requirements and constraints governing the development and use of polymer composites in automotive applications. It will focus on five factors among the requirements and constraints that retard the rapid growth in applications of automotive polymer composites. These challenges that remain retardants in meeting the cost, processing, performance, appearance and disposal requirements for these materials govern their acceptance in automotive application. The motives driving the industry to champion the development and implementation of these lightweight materials for energy-efficient vehicles will be presented in the context of the practical market requirements and constraints of the industry in order to show the importance of investing effort and resources to overcome these challenges.

Key Terms: automotive composites, polymer composites, composites needs and requirements

INTRODUCTION

The unrelenting drive to improve automotive energy efficiency and reduce the environmental impact of automotive manufacturing, vehicle operation and disposal, without compromising vehicle capacity, performance, appearance or price, has motivated innovative approaches to vehicle weight reduction. One such approach is to utilize low-cost polymer composites in semi-structural body applications. This approach requires rapid, robust, cost-effective materials and fabrication technologies that are compatible with automotive designs and manufacturing, and yet yield components that meet the requirements and constraints of the industry. These emerging automotive designs, materials and manufacturing technologies face new challenges as they advance the use of composites in automotive applications.

The need for this progress is intensifying as public awareness of our finite energy and environmental resources creates market, societal, and political pressures for more suitable, more fuel-efficient, environmentally-friendly vehicles at the affordable costs to which we have become accustomed. These pressures motivate a search for new materials, designs and processes. Several successful implementations will be mentioned as examples of how these materials can be used to support the drive toward the continuous improvements in performance, energy-efficiency, manufacturing cost and environmental conservation. Some remaining barriers to increased implementation will also be presented as indicators of further work needed.

Efforts to breach these barriers are underway and it can be seen that the journey to the objective will open unexplored technical territory and leave behind a wake of broken paradigms. Among them are the obvious paradigms of powertrain technology, accompanied closely by conventional body design or architecture, body materials and processes. These unconventional approaches become attractive paths to the increased fuel-efficient targets of the industry that are necessarily constrained by costs.

It is estimated that a 50% reduction in the weight of both body and chassis will be required to meet the goal of high energy efficiency, thus requiring innovative materials technology and designs. Additional major thrusts within this industry are to reduce the time to bring a vehicle from concept to production and to enhance environmental conservation. This wide spectrum of engineering and manufacturing objectives will require a simultaneous-engineering team approach.

Such an integrated, cross-functional team approach has made it clear that the mass production of high-volume automotive vehicles requires rapid cycle times, robust processing and reasonable costs. Moreover, such issues as appearance, performance and the recycling infrastructure must also be addressed. Champions of new materials and processes must also be aware of resistance to change that may be encountered in the manufacturing environment and be prepared to address and resolved it before the encounter. Discussing the first five of these familiar factors that retard or govern polymer composites growth in automotive body implementations will hopefully help to identify those areas where research, development and manufacturing efforts should be focused in order to breach those barriers and accelerate progress in this automotive materials technology.

This paper will focus on those five familiar factors retarding the growth of polymer composites in automotive applications. These factors are part of a long list that can be divided into five major categories. Each of these categories is well recognized as important areas of concern that must be addressed when new materials technologies are being investigated for application in the automotive industry. Many more than the five factors are included on the list to provide a degree of completeness, but most of them are beyond the scope of this paper. Moreover, some entries such as “part integration” and “tooling cost reduction” are not retardants to growth, but motivators. These also have been listed to offer a degree of completeness.

As expected, the list begins with cost, the category that must be addressed in order for polymer composites to compete with other less-expensive materials options. Manufacturing follows because this category is of major importance to an industry that depends on mass production methodologies and minimizing investment capital, labor intensity and operating costs to maintain the low cost and high value of its products.

Cost	Part Integration Tooling Cost Reduction Marginal Cost of Materials	Customer Acceptance
Manufacturing	Robust Fabrication Cycle Time Assembly Surface Coating	Internal (Manufacturing) Customers Manufacturing Process Compatibility Cosmetic Appearance Semi-Structural Appearance Damage Tolerance Damage Detection Repair Recycling
Properties	Physical Properties Isotropic or Anisotropic Mechanical Properties Structural Integrity Fiber-Resin Adhesion Isotropic or Anisotropic	External (Retail) Customers Cosmetic Appearance Semi-Structural Appearance Damage Tolerance Damage Detection Repair Recycling
Performance	Weight Reduction Stiffness and Strength Durability Crash Energy Management	Society and Regulatory Agencies Damage Tolerance Damage Detection Repair Recycling Disposal

An examination of this list reveals several entries that have been raised to prominence in recent years, as environmental stewardship has become more important to industry, society and regulatory agencies. Recycling and disposal issues could retard growth, unless the development of a composites recycling and disposal infrastructure is accelerated.

From the preceding list, five familiar factors that currently retard the growth of polymer composites in the automotive industry have been selected for the focus of this report. They are

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| <p>1. Cost
Marginal Cost of Materials</p> <p>2. Manufacturing
Robust Fabrication
Cycle Time
Assembly
Surface Coating</p> <p>3. Properties
Physical Properties
Isotropic or Anisotropic
Mechanical Properties
Structural Integrity
Fiber-Resin Adhesion
Isotropic or Anisotropic</p> <p>4. Performance
Weight Reduction
Stiffness and Strength</p> <p>5. Customer Acceptance
Internal (Manufacturing) Customers
Manufacturing Process Compatibility</p> | <p>5. Customer Acceptance (cont'd)
Cosmetic Appearance
Semi-Structural Appearance
Damage Tolerance
Damage Detection
Repair
Recycling</p> <p>External (Retail) Customers
Cosmetic Appearance
Semi-Structural Appearance
Damage Tolerance
Damage Detection
Repair
Recycling</p> <p>Society and Regulatory Agencies
Damage Tolerance
Damage Detection
Repair
Recycling
Disposal</p> |
|--|--|

A significant psychological retardant to growth is resistance to change. Although mentioned earlier, it has not been listed, nor will it be dealt with herein, because solving the technical issues and demonstrating customer acceptance can reduce this growth-retarding component. Moreover, the wide spectrum of human behavior over which such resistance to change is manifested is not easily dealt with effectively in a discussion designed to focus on materials and process technology issues.

Obviously, each item listed cannot be dealt with extensively within the limited scope of this paper, but a brief discussion of each should help direct the attention of those in the composites research community toward those areas of need in the automotive composites customer community. That is the intent of this paper.

COSTS

The advantages, disadvantages and benefits of manufacturing and operating light-weight, energy-efficient vehicles are examined here, by comparison with current prevailing available options in the automotive industry. This approach was taken because in order to make changes in, or replace any current technology with a new one, advantages of the new, compared with the old, must be established and customer acceptance demonstrated. Therefore, it must be recognized that when these composite materials and processes are applied in the automotive industry, they enter a metal-dominated world where designs, processes, and applications have traditionally accommodated metals. Non-metallic “engineered materials”, which differ significantly from metals in many chemical, physical, and mechanical properties, face notable challenges when entering this traditionally metal-dominated environment.

Perhaps the most significant among them is cost competition with steel. Steel has ruled the automotive industry as the material of choice for many years. There are well-known reasons for this dominance: low

cost, high performance that can be reliably predicted, an acceptable and/or manageable level of isotropic properties, familiar long-established forming technology, well-developed low-cost joining technology, corrosive-resistant coatings technologies and acceptable surface appearance. Any material that competes with steel in automotive applications must provide identifiable advantages that supercede the aforementioned, or the material must be capable of forming a component that will meet requirements that are not easily met by a low-cost steel component, while adding value. Obviously, the inertia of high capital investments in steel forming and joining equipment and manufacturing facilities offers significant resistance to any component replacement implementation in an unchanged design.

With the marginal cost of steel at about $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{1}{3}$ that of many polymer composites, on a cost-per-unit-mass basis, challenging engineering innovation is required to achieve reduced weight without sacrificing the cost-effectiveness, performance or value of the component. This implies that composites parts are not to be expected to replace steel parts on a part-for-part basis, but must take innovative approaches to replace steel components, assemblies and systems, reducing weight without adding an unbearable cost penalty. Often, the cost penalty is unbearable if greater than zero.

This approach to composites implementation is guided by carefully considering all materials and design options. Lightweight metal components are considered along with their cost. They generally come with relatively higher cost for their high performance. Low-cost steel is also considered as a candidate for lightweight applications because it lends itself to some innovative design concepts. Fiber-reinforced polymer composites (FRP) are considered as viable candidates, even though their performance (strength and modulus) may be considerably lower than the previously mentioned materials, yet their range of properties include regions of acceptable performance, with optimal performance-to-cost ratios. FRP components may not always be lower cost components than steel, but can provide reduced weight at lower cost than the lightweight metals and can provide lighter components than the low-cost steel, hence the motivation to move to FRP when practical and not cost-prohibitive.

It must be noted that there has been little correlation between the price of oil and the price of polymers. Although highly taxed and thoroughly refined, processed and blended, gasoline retails for about \$0.22/pound, with about \$0.05/pound of that being tax. Polymer composites for most engineering applications are sold for about \$1.35/pound to more than \$2/pound, wholesale. This is about seven times the retail price of gasoline, with tax included. Whereas much of this difference in price may be due to production costs and non-integrated value chains, some of it may be due to technology development recovery cost margins. Nevertheless, the gasoline and steel production industries have demonstrated that advancements in their respective technologies and integration of the value chains have driven cost down, even in the face of inflation, so that it is difficult to beat either of them as an automotive energy source or engineering material.

While low cost and compatibility in design, materials, process and application are obvious requirements, the recognition that low cost must be a criterion placed on component costs, not on cost-per-unit-mass or cost-per-unit-volume. The use of polymer composites can often provide part integration advantages and tooling cost reduction not available in steel components. On the other hand, current composite joining technology is usually more costly and less reliable than current steel joining technology. So component costs and assembly costs must be compared at the production volumes planned for a given vehicle design and performance criterion. Therefore the requirements for the vehicle and the production volumes planned must first be established before design materials and processes can be selected.

The discussion of these requirements can be reduced to two words: "low cost", in its broadest sense. For example, a safe vehicle minimizes the cost in terms of human suffering and misery to the individual and community. It also minimizes the losses to society, or units thereof, incurred due to inconvenience, injury or death resulting from vehicular mishaps. An affordable vehicle provides reliable transportation at costs that are commensurate with available financial resources allowed for acquisition, operation and maintenance.

Obviously, affordability is an essential, prerequisite requirement. Energy-efficiency minimizes the costs to energy-resources expended for the development, manufacture, use and disposal of the vehicle. The cost to the environment during development, manufacture, use and disposal must also be minimized in order for the vehicle to be considered “environmentally friendly”. Finally, the vehicle must provide value in terms of performance to expectations – capacity, quality, durability, and reliability must all minimize hassle, inconvenience and the negative value concomitant with the cost of poor quality.

Hence these components of cost are but a few examples of those that all combine to comprise the total or full life cycle cost to all of those finite resources expended to acquire, use and dispose of the vehicle. This total cost should be counted as a “fully accounted cost” and minimized systemically by optimizing each cost component. Thus a low-cost vehicle can enhance the quality of life by providing obvious advantages to individuals and society while maintaining good stewardship of our human, energy and environmental resources.

The high-volume, mass production of low margin products is a very cost-sensitive enterprise. Capital investment manufacturing process and material costs must be optimized to maximize value to the customer. The quality and performance-to-price ratio must be maximized in order to compete in a value-sensitive and very competitive market. Therefore, material and manufacturing cost must always be kept in mind and minimized where it can be done without reducing quality and value.

The following simple calculations illustrate the small (\$3,558) margin of cost increase a value-conscious customer in the United States might be willing to pay for energy efficiency at current fuel prices, if the customer were to govern the purchase decision simply by personal economics, while attributing little or no monetary value to environmental quality.

If fuel costs for traveling 100,000 miles in a 5-passenger car at 27 miles/gallon were 3,704 gallons x \$1.45/gallon = \$5,370; and in a 5-passenger car at 80 miles/gallon were 1,250 gallons x \$1.45/gallon = \$1,812, -- the difference in fuel costs would be \$3,558 (plus environmental costs).

The next scenario shows a larger margin (\$8,712) available for additional vehicle cost at fuel prices of \$3.55/gallon. If fuel costs for traveling 100,000 miles in a 5-passenger car at 27 miles/gallon were 3,704 gallons x \$3.55/gallon = \$13,149; and in a 5-passenger car at 80 miles/gallon were 1,250 gallons x \$3.55/gallon = \$4,437, the difference in fuel costs would be \$8,712 (plus environmental, economic, and political costs).

The results of these simple calculations, which do not include the time-value of money, must be considered when determining the additional costs available for materials or any other technology incorporated into an energy-efficient vehicle in various fuel-price markets where price/value competition is intense. Some customers, however, would be willing to spend more than the break-even price with fuel cost in order to contribute to the societal goals of improving environmental quality and reducing dependence on imported oil. This market has been shown to be sub-critically small in the United States by actual customer purchases, which confirm that the value per unit cost is the bottom line in most cases.

In fact, market-driven pressures indicate a reverse trend. The automotive market in the United States has shifted from smaller, more fuel-efficient passenger cars to light trucks, vans and sports-utility vehicles in order to obtain the capacity, performance and utility desired, even at the reduced fuel efficiency concomitant with heavier vehicles.

US automotive market data show the trends toward heavier vehicles that have occurred while reducing passenger car weights to improve their fuel efficiency. They also indicate that reducing vehicle size to reduce weight in order to improve energy efficiency may be counter productive in a market-driven economy where customers can simply switch to a larger class vehicle.

MANUFACTURING

In addition to the cost constraints discussed earlier, there are other dominant requirements and constraints that must be acknowledged and met for all advanced materials. Important among them are manufacturing issues that stand out in a high-volume automotive environment. Several of them are especially noteworthy for composite materials.

- Robust Fabrication
- Cycle Time
- Assembly
- Surface Condition and Coatings

Designs, manufacturing and assembly processes, as well as applications, must be optimized for each new material. This is especially true of composite materials because each composite component is an outcome of the individual (vs. batch) process that produces it. This concept underscores the required compatible fit among design, materials, process and application.

Robust processes are required in order to maintain an optimal operation in a typical non-ideal plant environment and to provide constant output of properties under varying plant processing conditions expected. Electron micrographs of polymer composite specimens show that there is considerable difficulty that remains in this area. The high aspect ratio of the reinforcement fibers (>30) tend to make them prone to align with resin flow vectors during the molding process and thus contribute to significant regional anisotropy in both physical and mechanical properties. Robust processes are also more amenable to automation, which can reduce labor intensity and the concomitant marginal piece costs.

Rapid processes are required to support synchronous production in high volume manufacturing and thus avoid costly inventory stack-up. Rapid processes require short cycle times for curing and cooling the polymer resin and fast, reliable assembly and joining technology. Robust, rapid and reliable adhesive bonding technology for joining some polymer composites, especially the polyolefins, has proven to be a challenging objective, yet to be achieved within the cost constraints permitted.

Nevertheless, upon achieving these objectives of cost, rapid and robust manufacturing and consistent material properties, polymer composites offer many noteworthy advantages. They include parts integration, design flexibility, low capital investment cost, weight reduction, corrosion resistance and engineered mechanical properties such as local anisotropy. These advantages motivate the pursuit of this ever-expanding materials technology for application in the advancing, competitive automotive world.

PROPERTIES

These advantages, however, do not come without risks. For example, the advantage of being capable of directional and regional anisotropy carries with it the risk of having mechanical properties in a given region or direction outside of specifications. Both the advantages and disadvantages are derived from the fact that the properties of each composite component are a function of the individual process by which it is fabricated as much as they are a function of the materials comprising it. Moreover, the properties vary as a function of the location and direction of the constituents, both of which are process dependent.

Evidence for this feature has been observed by the electron micrographs, where chopped glass fibers are randomly arranged in some isotropic regions of a specimen, but unintentionally aligned in other regions that are anisotropic. These regions are usually referred to as “flow lines”, because they result from flow-induced alignment during the molding process. This materials anisotropy problem is responsible for anisotropic mechanical properties. Mechanical test data derived from specimens with these fiber-alignments have

confirmed this many times on large molded parts. These anisotropic regions also contribute to internal residual stress that can reduce the isotropic design strength of the molded part.

This materials anisotropy problem is responsible for anisotropic physical properties in such as the coefficient of linear thermal expansion (CLTE), which causes the uneven shrinkage of molded parts upon cooling. This uneven shrinkage is also responsible for the “pie plate” doming and “potato chip” distortion of parts upon cooling. It also contributes to internal residual stress that can reduce the strength or increase the mechanical anisotropy of the molded part.

Another factor adversely impacted the structural integrity of the composite material is fiber-to-resin adhesion. This anomaly in the mechanical properties is observed when there is insufficient or ineffective sizing on the reinforcement fibers to provide reliable bonding to the resin under high stresses. This anomaly does not usually manifest itself at low stresses, because the weak bonding of the fibers to the resin provides the expected modulus, until the component is loaded to give stress levels where the fibers break clean from the resin. At that point, without the benefit of the reinforcement fibers contributing to local load-bearing, the part fails.

This problem has been observed more often in carbon fiber reinforced specimens than in those molded with glass fiber reinforcement. This observation indicates that more work is needed to improve the carbon fiber sizing to provide better high-stress adhesion to the resin for certain automotive fiber-resin combinations.

PERFORMANCE

Clearly, part performance results from a correct relationship among design, materials and the manufacturing process providing the structural integrity, appearance and performance expected to meet the requirements of the application. The impairment of mechanical properties, such as modulus and strength, are addressed in the preceding paragraphs in the section on “Properties”.

Two of the critical performance requirements of automotive body materials and designs are crash-energy management and modulus. Material modulus is required to provide the required stiffness over a wide range of expected operating temperatures. Both analytical and mechanical evaluations were undertaken to assure that these requirements are met and to enhance and validate analytical modeling techniques for these new automotive materials and assemblies.

The durability and crash-energy management of composite components were removed from the final list in the “Introduction” because these issues have been dealt with extensively, and addressed and resolved favorably by the Automotive Composites Consortium.

The issue of weight reduction remains. This issue is the prevailing reason to pursue the implementation of polymer composites in automotive applications, but this approach should not be undertaken blindly. That is, the simple substitution of polymer composites for other metals does not always yield weight reduction. The polymer composites approach to weight reduction must be carefully undertaken with materials engineering “due diligence” in which optimization of the relationship among design, materials and the manufacturing process is engineered to provide the structural integrity, appearance and performance expected to meet the requirements of the application.

CUSTOMER ACCEPTANCE

It is important to realize that the up-front involvement of the Manufacturing function in the early efforts of the simultaneous engineering cross-functional team is essential to the successful implementation of any new technology, and especially those technologies that require new materials, processes and equipment. This shared involvement and ownership by the Manufacturing function helps to address manufacturing issues

early, issues with which the Design and Engineering function may be unaware, and thus helps to shape the new technology, as well as the attitudes of those who must implement it, to better fit the environment in which it must be implemented. This approach enhances internal customer acceptance by eliminating the old traditional barriers between development engineering as supplier and manufacturing functions as the unwitting and often unwilling customer.

External customers have demonstrated no resistance to the acceptance of polymer composites in past automotive applications where the design, materials and process provided a good fit to the application and fit, finish, style, performance, quality, value, durability and appearance to the customer. In fact, these factors determine customer acceptance to a far greater degree than does the material used. Hence, several polymer composites have been successfully implemented in automotive applications without pro-plastic fanfare, thus providing real marketing data that supports the previous sentence.

Polymer composites in automotive applications support environmental conservation. The environmental assets derived from using plastic and polymeric composite materials are being considered more closely by the automotive industry. It has been determined that materials and processes used by the Corporation shall exceed all regulatory and customer requirements, as well as demonstrate good corporate citizenship and stewardship of the environment. To meet these needs in the future, it will be important to increase monitoring and evaluation of the full life cycle effects of these reinforced plastic compounds.

Lastly, recyclability and recycled content are becoming increasingly important. Furthermore, vehicle-end-of-life proposals, laws, and voluntary agreements, and the development of an international labeling standard under ISO 14021 (Environmental Labels and Declarations: Self-declared Environmental Claims), are causing manufacturers to evaluate materials based on both their ability to be recycled and the amount of recycled content of which they are comprised. Health and safety considerations must also be factored into the material selection decision.

EXAMPLES OF PROGRESS

Progress toward the objective of providing a body for a low-cost vehicle, fuel-efficient, full-size vehicle that meets the light-weight requirements for high energy efficiency will be reported. Several remaining challenges, such as providing a class "A" surface finish without paint will be addressed, and the next steps to overcome them will be outlined.

The Chrysler Composites Vehicle (CCV), originally designed and developed for an emerging market in developing nations, has become the vehicle that drove the initiation and continued development of large injection-molded body technology (LIMBT). This technology is now being developed to support the low-cost manufacture of a lightweight fuel-efficient, family-size vehicle, such as were described in the goals of the Partnership for a New Generation of Vehicles (PNGV). At DaimlerChrysler, this effort focused on molding a composite body for attachment to a metal frame. This approach was pursued in order to meet the fuel-efficiency, performance and capacity objectives of the PNGV while remaining within the cost constraints required by the US automotive market.

The low-cost, rapid assembly requirement is met by a design that reduces the body of the vehicle to four parts, plus doors, hood, etc. These four parts are full left and right inners and outers. When assembled by adhesive bonding or fusion welding, they provide box sections in critical structural areas where stiffness is required. In this manner, a fairly low-modulus (400ksi to 600 ksi or 3Gpa to 4Gpa) material is able to provide the stiffness required. Hence, the design, material and process all work together to support the application. The remaining challenges are achieving a class "A" in-mold surface finish and materials that are strong yet ductile over all operating temperatures.

The Dodge Intrepid ESX3 is the latest version of this operational hybrid concept vehicle and has been

shown and driven since early 2000 to demonstrate the fulfillment of DaimlerChrysler's Liberty objectives for 2000 AD. It features a low rolling resistance, low aerodynamic drag, light weight body and chassis system representing DaimlerChrysler's efforts in developing Large Injection Molded Body Technology (LIMBT). The low cost, lightweight plastic body technology is DaimlerChrysler's approach to compensating for the added cost of the hybrid powertrain. The vehicle weighs 1022 kg, has a coefficient drag of 0.20, seats 5 passengers, has more cargo space than a production Intrepid and is 0.23 meters shorter.

Many opportunities exist on the exterior of a vehicle for reinforced plastics, each with its own benefit and unique challenge. Examples of exterior components capable of utilizing reinforced plastics include bumper beams, fenders, front hoods, pillars, rear deck lids, body-in-white. These areas have a unique set of performance requirements that include mechanical properties, surface quality and weight. Materials that have resistance to cracking and denting as well as an increase in panel stiffness are necessary to meet higher customer expectations. Impact improvements are also necessary to meet crack and dent resistance objectives.

Surface quality of the exterior components is another requirement related to customer satisfaction. With an increasing emphasis on mold-in-color (MIC) or a molded-on coating (MOC) for exterior plastic components, greater development efforts will be necessary to maintain world class finish and meet customer expectations and manufacturing standards.

In order to meet these requirements, areas such as dimensional stability (to eliminate distortion issues) and weatherability improvements of these FRP type components are needed.

Weight reduction is important since each component covers a large surface area. Reducing panel thickness by utilizing reinforcements in plastics, such as hollow glass spheres, is one way to reduce weight. The use of composites and lighter weight metal materials such as aluminum on the exterior panels of the Plymouth Prowler is an example of how meeting weight reduction requirements while maintaining quality was achieved.

Mold-in-color (MIC) is another approach that offers substantial cost reduction benefits along with the potential still require development efforts to meet MIC capability to compete in "high gloss" and "smooth surface" applications. Improved surface quality, with greater scratch and mar resistance, is necessary to successfully meet MIC exterior appearance requirements.

CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

This polymer composites approach to molded body technology has the potential for reducing vehicle weight, manufacturing complexity and assembly cost, while providing a body with the appearance, performance and capacity currently extant in full-size, mass-produced vehicles. This technology has been successfully evaluated in several pre-production tests and evaluations performed in earlier programs.

This approach to meeting the low-cost, high-volume requirements for manufacturing an energy-efficient, family-size vehicle that looks and performs up to the expectations of today's customers, and yet can be acquired within the cost constraints imposed by economic and market realities continues to be attractive.

As the use of fiber-reinforced plastics increase in automotive components, the need to optimize the match of the material system with each specific application is emphasized. The development and selection of resins, fibers, and other additives, must consider all aspects of the application, and their impact on the environment. Innovative additive packages and reinforcement combinations will be needed to meet design requirements, manufacturing requirements, performance requirements and customer expectations. Moreover, the polymer composites approach to large molded body technology has high potential for meeting the goals of reducing

body weight, improving environmental impact, manufacturing complexity and cost, while yielding a vehicle with performance, appearance, capacity and price comparable to that available in current vehicles.

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